

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SCREENING OF PLANTS EXTRACTS WITH ANTIARRHYTHMIC ACTIVITY

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Abstract

The literary data about antiarrhythmic properties of plants are relatively scarce. We have chosen for study 30 species of insufficiently investigated Belorussian plants. The extract of *Crataegus sp.* was used for comparison, due to its well-known antiarrhythmic properties. The aconitine model of experimental arrhythmia of white rats was chosen for the screening. Almost 27% of studied species of plant possess antiarrhythmic activity. Therefore, antiarrhythmic screening with use of aconitine arrhythmia model may be an effective, fast and cheap method of plant preparations research.

Keywords: plants extracts, screening, aconitine model of arrhythmia, rats

Introduction. Last decades are marked by the increase of interest to the herbal medicine and to the development of new remedies of herbal origin, many of which are investigated insufficiently and as a consequence they are not used (or used very seldom) both in official, and in folk medicine. The literary data on antiarrhythmic properties of plants are relatively scarce. We proceeded from the point of view that heart arrhythmias are complication of various illnesses (first of all, various cardiovascular diseases) and the plant which cures these illnesses simultaneously has also preventive action on the arrhythmias emerging. Therefore, we have decided to resort to pharmacological study of preparations of those plants, on which there are references in the literature indicated on any cardiotropic action (i.e. changes of a pulse rate, arterial pressure, tonus of vessels etc), but their antiarrhythmic properties are not investigated at all or investigated very poorly. Only a few papers about antiarrhythmic plants have been published in last three decades, mostly about oriental plants [1-8]. In particular, antiarrhythmic properties of *Rhodiola rosea* [9] and garlic extract [10] were studied. The results of our work are presented briefly in International and European Conferences as posters [13-16].

Material and methods. We have chosen 30 species of Belorussian plants belonging to 21 botanical families for the study: *Aristolochiaceae* Juss. (Ar); *Asclepiadaceae* R.Br. (As); *Balsaminaceae* Rich. (Bals); *Boraginaceae* Juss. (Bor); *Convolvulaceae* Juss. (Con); *Crassulaceae* DC. (Crass); *Cruciferae* Juss. (Cr); *Fabaceae* Lindl. (Fab); *Fumariaceae* DC. (Fum); *Geraniaceae* Juss. (Ger); *Lamiaceae* Lindl. (Lam);

Liliaceae Juss. (Lil); *Loranthaceae* Juss. (Lor); *Monotropaceae* Nutt. (Mon); *Orobanchaceae* Vent. (Or); *Papaveraceae* (Pap); *Primulaceae* Vent. (Prim); *Ranunculaceae* Juss. (Ran); *Rubiaceae* Juss. (Rub); *Scrophulariaceae* Juss. (Scr); *Thymelaeaceae* Juss. (Thym).

The investigated plants are the following (in brackets botanical family is indicated): *Antitoxicum officinale* Pobed. (As), *Asarum europeum* L. (Ar), *Calystegia sepium* R. Br. (Con), *Chelidonium majus* L. (Pap), *Corydalis cava* Sch. (Fum), *Corydalis Halleri* Willd. (Fum), *Daphne mezereum* L. (Thym), *Erodium cicutarium* L'Her (Ger), *Fumaria officinalis* L. (Fum), *Galium verum* L. (Rub), *Geranium pratense* L. (Ger), *Glechoma hederacea* L. (Lam), *Hypopitys monotropa* Crantz. (Mon), *Impatiens noli-tangere* L. (Bals), *Lathraea squamaria* L. (Or), *Lycopus europaeus* L. (Lam), *Lunaria rediviva* L. (Cr), *Majanthemum bifolium* Schmidt (Lil), *Mellitis sarmatica* Klock. (Lam), *Ononis arvensis* L. (Fab), *Polygonatum officinale* All. (Lil), *Primula veris* L. (Prim), *Scutellaria gallericulata* L. (Lam), *Sedum acre* L. (Crass), *Sedum telephium* L. (Crass), *Sempervivum soboliferum* Sims. (Crass), *Symphitum officinale* L. (Bor), *Thalictrum minus* L. (Ran), *Veronica officinalis* L. (Scr), *Viscum album* L. (Lor). Extract of *Crataegus sp.* was used as standard preparation, due to its well-known antiarrhythmic properties. The collection and the definition of the plants species is made by professor Oleg Sozinov from Grodno University Department of Botany.

Overground part of the plants were extracted at room temperature with 20% alcohol in proportion of

1:10. One month later extracts were filtrated and investigated on the aconitine model of experimental arrhythmia of white rats [4]. The experiments were carried out on white rats of both sexes (100-200 g), in groups of 5-15 animals. The rats during the experiment were under intraperitoneal urethane anesthesia (1.5 g/kg). Extracts were injected into rat's femoral vein in doses of 0.25-3 ml/kg five minutes before injection of 0.001% aconitine solution in dose of 20-40 µg/kg. The aconitine dosage was fluctuated in each group of rats in order of obtaining of the arrhythmia appearance during strictly 2-3 min after arrhythmogen injection in control rats. Antiarrhythmic effects were estimated according to 1) arrhythmia latent period extension; 2) arrhythmia appearance prophylaxis; 3) arrhythmia duration shortening. These parameters were compared with analogous

ones after injection the same volume of 20% alcohol (control group).

Results. The experimental data obtained on the model of aconitine arrhythmia can be divided into three groups. The first one includes the plant's extracts not influencing the parameters of aconitine arrhythmia (18 species of the studied plants), the second group includes the plants with antiarrhythmic activity (8 species of plants, see the table below) and the third group includes the plant extracts with proarrhythmogenic action. *Viscum album L.*, *Daphne mezereum L.* and *Glechoma hederacea L.* extracts in all doses (0.25-3 ml/kg) had proarrhythmogenic action. These plant extracts caused arrhythmia latent period shortening or/and caused death of the rats.

Table 1

Antiarrhythmic action of plant extracts

Species of plants	Preventing of arrhythmia (%)	Arrhythmia latent period extension (times)	Changes of ECG after the plant extract
<i>Chelidonium majus</i>	20	2-3	None
<i>Corydalis cava</i>	60	2	Mild bradycardy*
<i>Corydalis Halleri</i>	0	3-16	None
<i>Crataegus sp</i>	60	None	None
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	12.5	2-10	None
<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	33	2-5	None
<i>Polygonatum officinale</i>	33	3-5	Mild bradycardy
<i>Sedum acre L.</i>	20	None	Mild bradycardy
<i>Thalictrum minus</i>	40	2	Moderate bradycardy**

* decrease of heart rate up to 20% from the native state;

** decrease of heart rate between 20-40 % from the native state.

Discussion. All mechanisms of herbal antiarrhythmic action can be conditionally divided into two groups: 1) antiarrhythmic drugs and 2) metabolic one.

The first group includes the study of *Chang-GJ et al.* [5], which indicates possible electrophysiological mechanisms for antiarrhythmic efficacy and positive inotrope action of liriodenine, natural aporphine alkaloid from *Fissistigma glaucescens*. It is concluded that, through the inhibition of natrium channels, liriodenine can suppress ventricular arrhythmias induced by myocardial ischaemia reperfusion. *Ozaki-Y.* [4] revealed antiarrhythmical activity of hirsutine (indol compound of *Uncaria rhynchophylla* Miq. and *Amsonia elliptica* Roem. et Schult.) on both aconitine-induced arrhythmia in mice and ouabain-induced arrhythmia in guinea pigs. The potency and, probably, mechanism of the action of hirsutine is similar to ajmaline, another indole compound. *H. P. T. Ammon et al.* [9, 10] indicated that preparations of *Crataegus* like many others antiarrhythmic agents exhibit negative inotropic effect. *Dai S. et al.* [3] confirmed that ethanol extract of *Sophora flavescens* Ait. caused depression in heart rate, both systolic and diastolic blood pressure and the elevation of ventricular fibrillation threshold by dogs, i.e. activities resembling those of antiarrhythmic agents. Earlier *Dai S. et al.* [2] revealed that the time of onset of cardiac arrhythmias induced by aconitine infusion in mice is significantly prolonged by the extract of *Sophora flavescens* Ait. The mechanisms of action of it are unclear, but the antiarrhythmic action is due to alkaloids [1]. *Martin N. et al.* [13] studied garlic dialysate (*Allium sativum L.*)

on arrhythmia by dogs and by isolated rat's atria. This extract decreased positive inotropic effect of isoprenaline and has significant antiarrhythmic effect in both ventricular and supraventricular arrhythmias. The second group ("metabolic") includes the study of *Lishmanov I. B. et al.* [12], which revealed that antiarrhythmic effect of *Rhodiola rosea* is associated with the induction of opioid peptides biosynthesis. *Arpad Tosaki et al.* [6, 7] indicates that *Ginkgo biloba* extract reduce the incidence of ventricular fibrillation and ventricular tachycardia. The possible mechanism of antiarrhythmic effect of *Ginkgo biloba* is connected with the inhibition of free radicals formation. But *Nobuya Haramaki et al.* [8] negates any significant antiarrhythmic action of *Ginkgo biloba*.

It is known that aconitine acts as an agonist of sodium membrane channels [16]. Due to this fact we can suppose that the substances of the extracts prevent the disruption of membrane sodium channels function. It is possible that it causes the typical membrane stabilizing effect like the antiarrhythmic agents of I class, which is proven by the experiments. Therefore, all adaptogenic or metabolic mechanisms like *Ginkgo* or *Rhodiola* that are possible for chronic experiments are excluded. We can make the conclusion too, that the antiarrhythmic properties of plants are coexisting mostly with their toxic properties (i.e. almost all plants with antiarrhythmic properties possess toxic properties). There isn't any correlation between antiarrhythmic activity of plant's extracts and changes of ECG after plant extract injection (see the table above).

Conclusion. Antiarrhythmic screening with the use of aconitine arrhythmia model may be an effective, fast and not sophisticated method of plant preparations research.

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